

*Operando Magic Angle Spinning solid-state NMR
spectroscopy of methanol photoreforming over ti-
tania-coated silica monoliths*

Supporting Information

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1. Experimental

1.1 Materials

Anatase (99.7%), ammonia solution (32%), nitric acid (65%), 2-nitrobenzaldehyde ($\geq 99.0\%$), Pluronic P-123 (M_N 5800), polyethylene glycol (PEG, average M_N 35000), tetraethyl orthosilicate (TEOS, $\geq 99\%$), and titanium(IV) isopropoxide (TTIP, 97%) were purchased from Sigma Aldrich. Sodium hydroxide ($\geq 97\%$) was purchased from VWR, calcium carbonate (98%) and 1,4-dinitrobenzene (98%) from Thermo Scientific. Deuterated solvents were purchased from Euriso-top, ^{13}C -labelled methanol (99 atom% ^{13}C) from CortecNet. All chemicals were used as received.

1.2 Synthesis of materials

1.2.1 Silica Monoliths

Silica monoliths were synthesized according to a modified literature procedure: In a typical synthesis, 2.119 g (48.1 mmol) polyethylene glycol were dissolved in a mixture of 18.372 g (1.02 mol) water and 1.782 g (18.4 mmol) HNO_3 while stirring at 500 rpm. After 30 min, the flask was placed in an ice bath and 15.0 g (72.0 mmol) TEOS were added. The solution was stirred at 700 rpm for 30 min until clear. Before filling the solution into appropriate molds, the solution was degassed by ultrasonication for 30 seconds. To maintain a stable solution, it is recommended to stir at 200 rpm while filling the molds. After filling, the molds were sealed and placed in a drying oven preheated to 40°C . After 3 days at 40°C , the monoliths are carefully removed from the molds, washed several times with distilled water to pH 7 and immersed in $1\text{ mol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ aqueous solution of NH_3 . The flask was sealed and placed in a drying oven at 40°C for 24 hours. Afterwards, the monoliths were washed with distilled water to pH 7, dried in a desiccator with a water reservoir for at least one week and finally calcined at 550°C for 8 hours (heating ramp $1\text{ K}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$).

1.2.2 Outer surface etching

To selectively etch away this dense outer layer of the silica monoliths, an etching paste consisting of 10.227 g (1.76 mmol) Pluronic P123, 89.6 mg (2.24 mmol) NaOH 263.2 mg (2.63 mmol), CaCO₃ and 4.3856 g (243.64 mmol) water was prepared. The mixture was stirred until a homogeneous paste was obtained. The outer surface of each monolith was covered with the paste. After 1 hour, the monoliths were washed with distilled water, immersed in distilled water and ultrasonicated twice for 3 minutes, dried in a desiccator with a water reservoir for at least one week and finally calcined at 400°C for 8 hours (heating ramp 1 K min⁻¹).

1.2.3 TiO₂ layer formation by atomic layer deposition in solution

Referring to the approach of atomic layer deposition from solution, the parent monoliths were carried with dipping method to be grafted.^[1] The monoliths were activated at 350°C under 10⁻³ mbar for 12 h before grafting. The solvent employed is anhydrous ethanol, 0.2 mol·L⁻¹ titanium isopropoxide (TTIP) in ethanol was used as titanium source, pure water was used for hydrolysis of TTIP. To remove any unreacted precursor of last half deposition step, the same volume of solvent was used for ultrasonically washing, and repeated several times with fresh solvent, before being dipped into another precursor solution. After 5, 10, and 20 cycles grafting, monoliths were dried slowly at room temperature under ethanol vapor for 48 h. Then monoliths were calcined at 550°C for 8 h with 1 K·min⁻¹ temperature ramping.^[2]

1.3 Operando photocatalytic MAS NMR experiments under light irradiation

Solid-state NMR experiments were carried out on a 500 MHz (11.74 T) wide-bore DD2 spectrometer by Agilent at room temperature. Powdered dry samples were packed into transparent 3.2 mm outer diameter sapphire rotors. Powders wetted with ¹³C-methanol were impregnated with the incipient wetness method and then packed into 3.2 mm sapphire rotors. Monoliths were impregnated with a given volume of solution and packed into 3.2 mm sapphire rotors (Figure

S1). A thin Teflon tape was placed into the rotor in a sling under the monolith and the ends of the tape were placed onto the monolith. This sling allowed to remove the tightly fitted monoliths from the rotor after completed analysis. Additional Teflon tape was placed on top of the monolith to fix the monolith tightly under the rotor cap (Figure S1). All impregnation and rotor packing steps were carried out under inert atmosphere.

MAS NMR spectra were recorded on a prototype HX wide-bore 3.2 mm LED MAS NMR probe developed by NMR Service Erfurt and equipped with 4 LEDs (365 nm, 1700 mA, Thorlabs, M365 FP1, controlled each by a DC 40 LED driver, Thorlabs) constantly irradiating the probe via glass fibers ending in between the turns of the RF coil. Rotors were spun at 11.5 kHz MAS at room temperature.

^1H spectra were recorded using the depth sequence to suppress probe background, consisting of a $\pi/2$ pulse of 3.75 ms followed by two π pulses of 5.5 ms, and phase cycled according to a combined “EXORCYCLE” and “CYCLOPS” scheme.^[3] Recycle times were set to 5 times T_1 . Longitudinal relaxation times (T_1) of ^1H were determined by saturation recovery experiments. ^{13}C direct excitation spectra were recorded with a $\pi/2$ pulse of 3.25-5 ms followed by signal acquisition with ^1H spin-64 decoupling at 71-90 kHz. Recycle times were set to 60 s. Deconvolution of ^{13}C CP MAS NMR spectra was done using DMFit.^[4]

1.4 Quantification of light irradiation efficiency in MAS NMR rotor

The light intensity at the inside of the MAS rotor was determined by a literature known actinometric system based on the photoisomerization of *ortho*-nitro benzaldehyde (*o*-NBA) to *ortho*-nitroso-benzoic acid.^[5-8] For the liquid actinometry different solutions were prepared by dissolving *o*-NBA in $\text{DCM-}d_2$. 30 μL of either solution were transferred into a sapphire rotor and inserted into the MAS NMR probe without spinning (see section 1.3). The samples were illuminated for a given time period, the illumination was turned off and ^1H spectra were recorded. After completing the ^1H NMR measurement the illumination was switched on again for

a given time. The decrease of the concentration of *ortho*-nitro benzaldehyde was calculated at various times and extrapolated to zero irradiation time.^[5]

In case of the silica monolith, a calcinated monolith (7.2 mg) was put into a sapphire rotor. A solution of *o*-NBA in DCM (13 μL , $1 \text{ mol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) was added. The monolith was stabilized in the sapphire rotor by a PTFE ribbon and ^1H NMR spectra were recorded at a MAS spinning speed of 8 kHz.

To directly compare the monolith shape with powder, monoliths were ground to powder by a hand mortar and activated under argon. A sapphire rotor was filled to half volume with the powder, *o*-NBA, dissolved in DCM (13 μL , $1 \text{ mol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) was added and the rest of the rotor was filled with more powder.

For calculation of the photon flux I° reaching the bottom of the probe, the photon flux of each LED was measured using a thermopile sensor (PowerMax-USB UV/VIS, Coherent) by directly connecting the glass fiber to the thermopile using a collimating lens (COL-UV/VIS, Avantes).

1.5 SEM and TEM analyses

SEM images of a $\text{TiO}_2@\text{SiO}_2$ monolith were taken on a Zeiss Gemini 560 (Zeiss Microscopy, Germany) with the InLens SE detector at 2 kV acceleration voltage. 50 times line integration was chosen to reduce charging artifacts and noise in the image. Additional low magnification images were taken at 5 kV using the InLens SE and ESB BSE detectors with 70 frames integrated and activated drift compensation. No coating was applied to the samples before the SEM imaging to preserve full visibility of all mesopores.

A standard lift-out procedure using a FEI Helios Nanolab 660 (Thermo Fisher Scientific) dual-beam FIB/SEM was employed to prepare the TEM lamella. The sample was coated outside the SEM with 50 nm of carbon in a Leica EM ACE 200 (Leica Microsystems) carbon coater to avoid sample drift and charging during lamella preparation. A representative region of interest (ROI) containing both the strut surface with the TiO_2 surface layer and a fractured silica strut

region was chosen. Additional 3 μm of carbon were deposited with the gas injection system of the FIB/SEM using first electron- and then ion beam induced deposition (EBID, IBID). This layer protects the ROI and leads to a more uniform milling. The final size of the lamella was 13 μm wide and 8 μm high with a thickness of around 100 nm.

TEM analysis was carried out on a FEI Titan Themis³ 300 (Thermo Fisher Scientific) operated at 300 kV equipped with a Super-X detector. EDXS maps were acquired using the high-angle annular dark-field (HAADF) STEM mode on six different areas of the lamella with a beam current of 150 pA and a varying number of frames ranging from 150 to 250. The pixel size of the mappings ranged from 0.77 to 1.5 nm. The EDXS data was analyzed using Velox 3.12 (Thermo Fisher Scientific). An averaging pre-filter with a size of 3 px and a multi-polynomial background correction with an order of 2 and automatic background windows was chosen. The spectra were quantified with a sample thickness of 100 nm, the Brown – Powell ionization cross-section model and an optimized spectrum fit. HRTEM images were taken with a beam current of 5.5 nA, a dwell time of 500 ms and by integrating 10 frames. Selected area electron diffraction (SAED) patterns were acquired in a surface near region and deeper inside the silica structure using a beam current of 235 pA, an exposure time of 1 second with integrating 50 frames with a parallel electron beam on specimen areas around 700 nm in diameter. To determine the anatase nanoparticle size (size of the coherently scattering volume), a Scherrer analysis of the SAED pattern in Figure S9b was performed. After rotational averaging (using DifTools PlugIn in Gatan Digital Micrograph v3.50.3584.0), spline-function based background subtraction and Gaussian peak fitting (using Fityk 1.3.1), the anatase nanoparticle size resulted in $L_{(101)} = 5.95$ nm and $L_{(004)} = 5.83$ nm using the integral breadth of the Gaussian peaks of (101) and (004), and a shape factor of 0.89 for spherical particles.^[9]

1.6 Pair Distribution Function Analysis (PDF)

X-ray total scattering data were measured on a STOE STADI P diffractometer equipped with a curved germanium (111) monochromator, four MYTHEN2 R 1K detectors and using Mo $K_{\alpha 1}$ radiation. Powders were packed into thin-walled (0.01 mm) borosilicate glass capillary (0.9 mm diameter). Measurements were performed from $Q_{\min} = 0.279 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$ to $Q_{\max} = 16.78 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$. To cover the complete 2θ regime ($-4 - 142.595^\circ$) two different detector positions were used. For each position the measurement time was set to 300 s and the measurements were repeated for a total of 20 h. Additional scattering measurements from empty capillary were performed in the same conditions for background correction. Raw data were treated using the PDFgetX3 program^[10] to obtain the experimental total PDF $G(r)$ function, using the chemical as determined by ICP analysis (Table S1) and the following parameters: $Q_{\min} = 0.35 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$, $Q_{\max} = 16 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$, $r_{\text{poly}} = 1.1$.

To highlight the contribution of TiO₂-based atom pairs to the $G(r)$ curve in the TiO₂@SiO₂ monolith, differential PDF analysis was applied to calculate the $\Delta G(r)$ curve (Figure S6b). Prior to subtracting the $G(r)$ curve of the pristine SiO₂ monolith from the $G(r)$ curve of the TiO₂@SiO₂ monolith, both $G(r)$ curves were normalized to the contribution of Si-O atom pair at 1.6 Å.

1.7 General Characterization

Inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectroscopy analysis (ICP-OES) was done using a SPECTRO Ciros-CCD. Prior to ICP OES analysis, ~100 mg of silica monolith were digested in a mixture of 6 mL HF, 4 mL HCl and 2 mL HNO₃ inside a Teflon lined autoclave using a Berghof-Microwave Digester-Speedwave 4 ($\theta_{\max} = 200 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, $p_{\max} = 50 \text{ bar}$, 37 min).

Nitrogen physisorption experiments were carried out using an ASAP 2000 (Micromeritics), Ar physisorption isotherms were recorded on a Autosorb-1-MP equipped with a CryoSync operating at 87.3 K (both Quantachrome). Prior to measurements the samples were degassed at 250°C under vacuum overnight. Pore size distributions were obtained from Ar physisorption

isotherms using dedicated DFT kernels for silica surfaces (spherical/cylindrical pores, NLDFT equilibrium).

Prior to mercury intrusion porosimetry (MIP), sample density was determined using a PORO-TEC pycnometer. MIP was performed using a Pascal 140 and 440 instrument (Thermo Fisher Scientific Inc.). Data were evaluated using the Washburn equation for cylindrical geometry and assuming a contact angle of 141° for both SiO_2 and TiO_2 surfaces.^[11,12]

2. Additional Figures

Figure S1. A: Typical pack monoliths into a sapphire rotor, B to E: Rotor packed with PTFE string used for lifting monoliths intact out after reaction.

Figure S2. Percentage of shrinkage of monoliths during gelation, drying and calcination, compared for different starting diameters of the monoliths. The shrinkage percentage is remarkably reproducible for different starting diameters and was determined to 16 %.

Figure S3. a) Ar physisorption isotherms recorded at 87 K of pristine SiO₂ monolith (black) and TiO₂@SiO₂ monolith after 5 sALD cycles (red). b) Corresponding pore size distribution derived from DFT kernels (color-code as in a). c) MIP curves of pristine SiO₂ monolith (black) and TiO₂@SiO₂ monolith (red) as well as crushed TiO₂@SiO₂ monolith (purple) over the interior pressure regime (pore size) and d) corresponding pore size distribution.

Ar and N₂ physisorption isotherms reveal for all monolithic materials the presence mesopores (maxima of the pore size distribution from Ar: 16.5 nm (5cyTiO₂@SiO₂ monolith) and 21 nm (SiO₂ monolith), Figure S3 a,b, & Figure S17), while mercury intrusion porosimetry (MIP) reveals additional macropores with diameters of approx. 1 μm (Figure S3 c, d). Note that the macropore network is partially retained after crushing the monoliths into a powder with a sharp contribution around 1 μm. However, the crushing leads to interparticular pore space, characterized by a broad pore size distribution between 10 to 100 μm.

By depositing TiO₂ on the silica monoliths, the meso- and macropore pore volumes and diameters are affected. Please note that the data shown in Figure S are not corrected for the mass increase by the deposition of TiO₂, resulting in a decrease of total pore volume by (i) decreasing the pore size of meso and macropores and (ii) simultaneously increasing the mass of the materials and thus its density. Note, that for the evaluation of MIP data, knowledge of the contact angle between the surface and Hg is required. Based on literature reports we assume that the contact angle for both surfaces is similar (141°^[11,12]). The contact angle is required to calculate from the measured pressure (p) the pore size according to the Washburn equation for cylindrical geometry:

$$d_p = \frac{-4 \cdot \gamma \cdot \cos \theta}{p} \quad [14]$$

However, we cannot exclude a systematic error in this assumption, mainly the impact of surface hydroxyl groups on the contact angle, which might slightly shift the resulting pore size distribution. For completely dehydroxylated silica surfaces the contact angle shifts to 105°.^[15]

Table S1. Overview of experimental data for pristine SiO₂ monolith, TiO₂@SiO₂ monolith and commercial anatase powder. ^a from BET equation between 0.01 < p/p_0 < 0.1, ^b at $p/p_0 = 0.99$, ^c from MIP, ^d for pores larger than 50 nm.

sample	SiO ₂	5cyTiO ₂ @SiO ₂	Anatase
Ti in wt%	0.00	7.85	n.d.
$S_{\text{BET}}^{\text{a}}$ / m ² /g	400	350	65
V_{p}^{b} / cm ³ /g	1.13	0.86	0.29
V_{p}^{c} / cm ³ /g	3.6	2.9	1.5
$V_{\text{p,macro}}^{\text{c,d}}$ / cm ³ /g	2.5	2.1	1.2
$S_{\text{macro}}^{\text{c,d}}$ / m ² /g	5.1	4.5	10.5

Figure S4. Low magnification SEM images of the $\text{TiO}_2@\text{SiO}_2$ monolith after 5 sALD cycles of TiO_2 deposition with (a) secondary electrons (SE) and (b) backscattered electrons (BSE) showing the homogenous macroporous structure of the SiO_2 monolith over a large scale.

Figure S5. (a) HAADF-STEM image of the TEM lamella of the $\text{TiO}_2@\text{SiO}_2$ monolith. Marked in green are the areas from which EDXS maps are taken (cf. Figure S7). The area marked in red contains the regions shown in the HRTEM images in Figure S8. The blue circle marks the area of the selected area diffraction aperture used to acquire the SAED pattern in Figure S9. (b)

Higher magnification HAADF-STEM image of the area marked in orange in (a). The vertical stripes result from curtaining artifacts introduced during FIB milling.

Figure S6. Additional HAADF-STEM images and corresponding STEM-EDXS maps. Intensity of silicon (red) ranges from 0 to 30 atomic percent, titanium (green) from 0 to 10 percent. (a) 1.5 μm deep measurement (area 2 in Figure S5a) with (b) magnified area at the coated surface revealing titania signal and a dense silica layer at the surface, and constant titania signal deep down into the mesoporous silica structure. (c) Surface corner with coated surface structure including the dense silica layer (left side) and fractured strut surface lacking the dense silica layer but featuring a constant titania signal (right side; area 3 in Figure S6a). (d) Fracture surface with constant titania signal but no dense silica layer (area 4 in Figure S6a).

Figure S7. Diffractograms of pristine SiO₂ monolith (black), 5 cycles of TiO₂@ SiO₂ monolith (red) and anatase nanoparticles (light gray). For comparison also the pXRD pattern of a TiO₂@ SiO₂ monolith after 20 cycles of SALD is shown (dark green), confirming that the shoulder at 23.3 ° in the red curve as well as the weak peaks at about 48, 54.4 and 62.7° are stemming from tiny anatase crystallites. Bragg markers: nanocrystalline TiO₂ (ICSD:1546049, CCDC: 1671232 ^[13]).

Figure S8. (a) HRTEM image of the silica monolith surface (diagonally positioned on the left side) with titania nanoparticles on top and inside the mesoporous silica (red area in Figure S6a). The dotted orange box marks the area of the FFT shown in Figure S9a. (b) Magnified image of

the blue area that shows lattice fringes (indicated with orange lines) of several titania nanoparticles inside the silica monolith. (c) Magnified image of the green area that shows lattice fringes (indicated with orange lines) of several titania nanoparticles on top of the monolith's surface.

Figure S9. (a) Fast Fourier transform (FFT) of the dotted orange area of the HRTEM image in Figure S8a indicating that the observable lattice fringes belong to the anatase phase. (b) SAED pattern of the blue circle indicated in Figure S6a showing the characteristic diffraction rings for the anatase phase. Expected diffraction ring positions for the anatase phase belonging to the corresponding lattice plane distances are indicated and indexed in (a) and (b).

Figure S10. a) $G(r)$ curves of SiO_2 monolith (dark gray) and $\text{TiO}_2@/\text{SiO}_2$ monolith (red). The dominant peaks in both $G(r)$ plots are assigned to the relevant inter-atomic distances of silica:^[16,17] 1.64 Å (Si-O), 2.64 Å (Si Å Si), 3.10 Å (Si Å Si) and 4.09 Å (Si Å O). b) The insert shows the differential PDF to highlight the contribution of the TiO_2 phase to the $G(r)$ curves of $\text{TiO}_2@/\text{SiO}_2$ monolith.

Figure S11. Evolution of ^1H spectra of an 0.91 M *o*-NBA solution in DCM-d_2 with increasing irradiation. The highlighted peak at 10.5 ppm corresponds to the aldehyde H of *o*-NBA. The large peak 7.9 ppm corresponds to all four aromatic protons of *o*-NBA. The decay of the aldehyde signal is visible over time. However, there is also a decay of the aromatic signal as well, due to “inner filter” effects and precipitation of *o*-NBAH at higher conversion.

Table S2. Overview of experimental conditions for evaluation of photon flux reaching the inner part of the rotor using *o*-NBA dissolved in DCM. ^a reaction in benzene and using another set of

glass fiber cables (FT400UMT instead of M113L01, both from Thorlabs).^b using 26 μl instead of 13 μl .

Insert in the rotor	$[o\text{-NBA}] / \text{M}$	$dn(o\text{-NBA}) / \text{mol/s}$	$I_0 / \text{mol/s}$	$I^\circ / \text{mol/s}$	$\frac{I_0}{I^\circ} / \%$	$I'_0 / \mu\text{mol/s}$
none	0.015	$4.55 \cdot 10^{-9}$	$1.45 \cdot 10^{-8}$	$1.36 \cdot 10^{-7}$	10.6	483
	0.91	$6.54 \cdot 10^{-9}$	$1.31 \cdot 10^{-8}$		9.6	436
Silica monolith	1	$3.46 \cdot 10^{-9}$	$6.91 \cdot 10^{-9}$	$1.36 \cdot 10^{-7}$	5.1	532
Crushed silica monolith	1	$1.77 \cdot 10^{-9}$	$3.54 \cdot 10^{-9}$	$1.36 \cdot 10^{-7}$	2.6	272

Figure S12. *Operando* ^{13}C CP NMR spectra of photoreforming of methanol over $\text{TiO}_2@\text{SiO}_2$ monolith. To all spectra 20 Hz line broadening were applied.

Figure S13. ^{13}C DE NMR spectra of MeOH exposed to a $\text{TiO}_2@ \text{SiO}_2$ monolith for 80h in the dark.

Figure S14. Operando ^{13}C DE MAS NMR spectra of photocatalytic methanol over ground $\text{TiO}_2@ \text{SiO}_2$ monolith at 11.5 kHz. 20 Hz line broadening were applied to all spectra.

Figure S15. Yield of side products and conversion of methanol (red) for photoreforming of methanol over $\text{TiO}_2@ \text{SiO}_2$ monolith. Data are derived from *operando* ^{13}C DE NMR spectra (Figure 2b).

Table S3. Comparison of conversion of methanol per g of Ti between the intact and the ground $\text{TiO}_2@ \text{SiO}_2$ monolith.

Sample	m / g	$V(^{13}\text{CH}_3\text{OH}) / \mu\text{L}$	$\beta_{\text{Ti}} / \text{wt}\%$	conversion (82 h) / $[\text{mmol}_{\text{MeOH}}/\text{g TiO}_2]$
intact monolith	0.0079	4.5	0.0785	80.67
ground monolith	0.01167	5	0.0785	47.93

Figure S16. Comparison of conversion based on reforming methanol per g of Ti between the intact and the ground $\text{TiO}_2@\text{SiO}_2$ monolith. Data are derived from *operando* ^{13}C DE NMR spectra of $\text{TiO}_2@\text{SiO}_2$ monolithic catalyst (Figure 2b) and *operando* ^{13}C DE NMR spectra of over ground $\text{TiO}_2@\text{SiO}_2$ monolith (Figure S10).

Figure S17. a) Comparison of N_2 physisorption isotherm recorded at 78 K of commercial anatase (light gray), SiO_2 monolith (dark gray) and $\text{TiO}_2@\text{SiO}_2$ monolith (red). b) MIP curve of commercial anatase.

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